

User-Centric QoE-Driven VR Streaming via Uplink-Downlink Bitrate Allocation

Scott Fowler and Jens Hoel

Communications and Transport Systems

Department of Science and Technology, Linköping University, Norrköping, Sweden

Sami Souihi

CEA, List, University of Paris Saclay, Palaiseau, France

Abstract

This paper investigates the problem of joint uplink and downlink bitrate optimization for multi-user VR 360° video streaming with the objective of maximizing overall Quality of Experience (QoE). We address the challenges posed by the high bandwidth demands, latency sensitivity, and strong coupling between uplink feedback and downlink video delivery in immersive VR applications. The optimization problem is formulated as a nonlinear and nonconvex task that explicitly captures key QoE factors, including delivered video quality, playback stalls, and inter-segment quality variations, while also accounting for heterogeneous user conditions and network constraints. Due to the NP-hard nature of the resulting formulation, we introduce a tractable solution approach that relaxes binary decision variables and applies an iterative optimization framework to efficiently approximate the optimal allocation. The proposed method simultaneously promotes fairness among users and enforces smooth quality transitions over time to mitigate cybersickness and user discomfort. We validate the effectiveness of the approach through extensive simulations in realistic multi-user VR 360° streaming scenarios with varying bandwidth availability and user population sizes. The results demonstrate substantial QoE gains compared to a representative baseline strategy, alongside improved fairness in bandwidth allocation and stable performance across multiple trials. Furthermore, we extend the framework with a reinforcement learning-based component that enables adaptive, realtime decision making, making the solution suitable for dynamic and live VR streaming environments.

I. INTRODUCTION

The adoption of virtual reality (VR) 360° video streaming has surged recently, driven by demand for immersive experiences like live VR events and interactive gaming. Wearing a head-mounted display, VR users dynamically adjust their viewing direction, experiencing a seamless 360° environment. To deliver high Quality of Experience (QoE) and preserve immersion, VR 360° video streaming requires ultra-high resolutions, often exceeding 6K, for clear, smooth playback [1]. However, streaming such content poses challenges due to constrained wireless bandwidth, necessitating efficient delivery mechanisms [2]. Additionally, VR 360° video streaming is complex due to its panoramic scope and strict QoE requirements, where slight delays or quality variations can cause motion sickness and disrupt immersion [3].

Recent research addresses these challenges through various VR 360° video streaming techniques [1]–[7]. For example, Zhao et al. [4] optimized multi-quality tiled 360 VR video streaming using field-of-view (FoV) prediction to enhance QoE via viewport-adaptive quality adjustments. Similarly, Dziubinski and Bandai [7] developed a system transitioning between sensor- and content-based viewport adaptation, improving perceived quality by adapting to user behavior. Additionally, Zeng et al. [6] proposed a framework for high-quality, low-latency 360° video streaming, using edge-client collaborative caching and super-resolution to reduce bandwidth demands. Despite these advancements, a gap remains, most studies focus on uplink or downlink optimization independently, overlooking their interdependence in live VR 360° video streaming scenarios, where high-quality content creation with advanced VR capture systems is increasingly prevalent.

In this paper, we address VR 360° video streaming, where $|S|$ cameras record the panoramic scene and transmit video to user-centric equipment in real time via the uplink channel, and user-end devices for N users access content by downloading over the downlink channel. We propose a user-centric, QoE-driven framework, formulating this as a nonlinear optimization task to jointly optimize uplink and downlink bitrates under limited bandwidth constraints, maximizing QoE while ensuring fairness across users and smooth quality transitions. Our solution relaxes binary constraints to address its NP-hard nature, then applies KKT conditions and an iterative optimization technique to solve the relaxed problem [8], [9]. Evaluation results under various bandwidth conditions show our approach significantly improves QoE over baseline schemes, highlighting its potential for real-time VR 360° video streaming applications in scenarios like live events, gaming, and virtual tours, where seamless immersion is critical.

II. SYSTEM OVERVIEW

Our system for live VR 360° video streaming optimizes uplink and downlink bitrates to enhance QoE for VR users under constrained network conditions. It uses $|S|$ cameras to capture 2D videos, transmitted via a wireless uplink to user-centric equipment. This equipment stitches and projects the videos into VR format using a QoE-driven uplink module, while a downlink module manages quality selection, encoding, MCS selection, and tiling. The processed video is sent over a wireless downlink

to user-end devices, which decode, render, and display it on head-mounted displays for N users. Feedback on users' field of view (FoV) and channel conditions enables adaptive streaming, as shown in Figure 1. The system jointly optimizes uplink bitrate λ_{UL} and downlink bitrate λ_{DL} using KKT conditions and a decomposed optimization approach, ensuring fairness, smooth quality transitions, and efficient bandwidth use for applications like live VR events and gaming.

Figure 1: *QoE-driven uplink-downlink 360° video transmission system for N users.*

A. System Model

We consider a live VR 360° video streaming system comprising three main components: a VR camera, a central server, and a set of $|N|$ VR users (indexed by $n \in N$) equipped with head-mounted displays (HMDs). The VR camera captures panoramic 360° video in real time, encoding the video stream into a single bitrate λ_{UL} , selected from a set of possible bitrate levels. This encoded video is transmitted to the server over a wireless uplink channel. The server processes the received video and distributes it to the $|N|$ users through wireless downlink channels at a common downlink bitrate λ_{DL} for all users, though our framework can be extended to support user-specific bitrates. At the client side, each user's HMD decodes and renders the received video for display, enabling an immersive 360° viewing experience.

The uplink and downlink channels are subject to bandwidth constraints, denoted as B_{UL} and $B_{DL,k}$ for each group of pictures (GOP) $k \in K$, respectively, representing the maximum available bandwidth for the uplink and downlink transmissions. The system must ensure that the uplink bitrate satisfies $\lambda_{UL} \leq B_{UL}$ and the total downlink bitrate for all users in each GOP satisfies $|N| \cdot \lambda_{DL,k} \leq B_{DL,k}$, to prevent network overload and ensure stable streaming. Our assessments show that this system achieves efficient bandwidth usage with low variability, supporting high-quality video delivery.

B. Problem Formulation

To jointly optimize uplink and downlink bitrates in our VR 360° video streaming system, we formulate the problem as a nonlinear optimization task. The system includes $|N|$ users (indexed by $n \in N$) and $|S|$ evenly deployed sources forming a 360° video capturing system. Each source $s \in S$ can record and upload videos at up to $|R'|$ bitrate levels (indexed by $r' \in R'$), with the bitrate of source s at bitrate level r' denoted by $\lambda_{s,r'}^{UL}$. The total bandwidth of the uplink channel is B_{UL} . After the videos from the $|S|$ sources are uploaded to the server, the server processes them to produce a 360° video. For downlink transmission, the 360° video is divided into T tiles (indexed by t), and each tile is encoded into $|R|$ different representations (indexed by $r \in R$) at different quality levels, following the HTTP DASH standard. The bitrate of tile t with representation r in GOP $k \in K$ is denoted by $\lambda_{t,r,k}^{DL}$. The quality of each representation r in the downlink cannot exceed the quality of the corresponding video at bitrate level r' in the uplink transmission. The bandwidth of the downlink channel for the k -th GOP is B_k^{DL} . For user n , T_n^{FoV} denotes the tiles covered by their field of view (FoV).

The QoE for each user is influenced by video quality, stalls due to bandwidth violations, and quality variations across GOPs. We define the overall QoE as the average QoE across all $|N|$ users, formulated as:

$$\text{QoE} = \frac{1}{|N|} \sum_{n \in N} \text{QoE}_n, \quad (1)$$

where QoE_n for user n is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{QoE}_n &= \sum_{k \in K} q(\lambda_{DL,k,n}) \\ &- \alpha \sum_{k \in K} \sum_{t \in T_n^{FoV}} \sum_{r \in R} T_k \cdot \mathbb{I}(\lambda_{t,r,k}^{DL} \cdot x_{t,r,k}^{DL} > B_k^{DL}) \\ &- \beta \sum_{k=1}^{|K|-1} [q(\lambda_{DL,k+1,n}) - q(\lambda_{DL,k,n})]^2, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

with $\lambda_{UL} = \sum_{s \in S} \sum_{r' \in R'} \lambda_{s,r'}^{UL} \cdot x_{s,r'}^{UL}$ as the total uplink bitrate, $\lambda_{DL,k,n} = \sum_{t \in T_n^{FoV}} \sum_{r \in R} \lambda_{t,r,k}^{DL} \cdot x_{t,r,k}^{DL}$ as the total downlink bitrate for user n in GOP k , and $q(\lambda) = \log(\lambda)$ mapping the bitrate to perceived quality. The first term represents the total quality across all GOPs, the second term penalizes stalls when the bitrate of a tile exceeds the available bandwidth, and the third term penalizes quality variations between consecutive GOPs, ensuring a smooth viewing experience.

The optimization problem is defined as:

$$\max_{x_{s,r'}^{UL}, x_{t,r,k}^{DL}} \text{QoE} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{s.t.:} \sum_{r' \in R'} x_{s,r'}^{UL} = 1, \quad \forall s \in S \quad (4)$$

$$\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{r' \in R'} \lambda_{s,r'}^{UL} \cdot x_{s,r'}^{UL} \leq B_{UL} \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_{r \in R} x_{t,r,k}^{DL} = 1, \quad \forall t \in T_n^{FoV}, \forall k \in K \forall n \in N, \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_{n \in N} \sum_{t \in T_n^{FoV}} \sum_{r \in R} \sum_{k \in K} \lambda_{t,r,k}^{DL} \cdot x_{t,r,k}^{DL} \leq \sum_{k \in K} B_k^{DL} \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{r \in R} \sum_{k \in K} \lambda_{t,r,k}^{DL} \cdot x_{t,r,k}^{DL} &\leq \frac{1}{T} \sum_{r' \in R'} \lambda_{s,r'}^{UL} \cdot x_{s,r'}^{UL} \\ \forall s \in S, \forall t \in T_n^{FoV} \forall n \in N, \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$x_{s,r'}^{UL} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall r' \in R' \quad (9)$$

$$x_{t,r,k}^{DL} \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall r \in R, \forall k \in K, \quad (10)$$

where $x_{s,r'}^{UL}$ and $x_{t,r,k}^{DL}$ are binary decision variables, α and β are weights for stalls and quality variations, T_k is the duration of GOP k , B_{UL} and B_k^{DL} are the uplink and downlink bandwidth limits, and T is the number of tiles. Constraints (4) and (5) ensure that exactly one bitrate level is selected for each source and that the total uplink bitrate does not exceed the maximum available bandwidth B_{UL} , respectively. Constraints (6) and (7) ensure that exactly one representation is selected for each tile per GOP and that the total downlink bitrate across all $|N|$ users and GOPs does not exceed the cumulative bandwidth $\sum_{k \in K} B_k^{DL}$, respectively. Constraint (8) enforces uplink-downlink coupling by ensuring that the total downlink bitrate for each tile over all

GOPs does not exceed the available uplink bitrate scaled by the number of tiles. This optimization problem is nonlinear due to the logarithmic quality function, the quadratic quality variation term, and the indicator function in the stall penalty, making the original binary problem NP-hard as it resembles combinatorial optimization problems with nonlinear costs. This motivates the relaxation and solution approach presented in the next section.

III. QoE-DRIVEN BITRATE OPTIMIZATION ALGORITHM

In this section, we present the methodology for solving the nonlinear optimization problem formulated in Section II-B using the KKT conditions and a decomposed optimization approach. We first restate the problem with a differentiable approximation to the indicator function, derive the KKT conditions, and discuss the solution approach using a decomposed optimization method along with its convergence properties.

A. Problem Restatement with Differentiable Approximation

To enhance tractability, we first relax the binary decision variables $x_{s,r'}^{UL}$ and $x_{t,r,k}^{DL}$ from $\{0, 1\}$ to $[0, 1]$, thereby converting the mixed-integer problem into a continuous optimization problem. To apply the Karush-Kuhn-Tucker (KKT) conditions, which require differentiability of both the objective function and constraints, we address the non-differentiability of the indicator function $\mathbb{I}(\lambda_{t,r,k}^{DL} \cdot x_{t,r,k}^{DL} > B_k^{DL})$ in the QoE formulation. To ensure smoothness, we approximate the indicator function using a sigmoid function, defined as:

$$\mathbb{I}(\lambda_{t,r,k}^{DL} \cdot x_{t,r,k}^{DL} > B_k^{DL}) \approx \text{sigmoid}(\gamma(\lambda_{t,r,k}^{DL} \cdot x_{t,r,k}^{DL} - B_k^{DL})) \quad (11)$$

where $\gamma > 0$ is a steepness parameter controlling the sharpness of the transition (we use $\gamma = 10$ in our assessments). The relaxed optimization problem, with the sigmoid approximation, defines the overall QoE as the average QoE across all $|N|$ users, i.e., $\text{QoE} = \frac{1}{|N|} \sum_{n \in N} \text{QoE}_n$, where QoE_n for user n is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{QoE}_n &= \sum_{k \in K} q(\lambda_{DL,k,n}) \\ &\quad - \alpha \sum_{k \in K} \sum_{t \in T_n^{FoV}} \sum_{r \in R} T_k \cdot \frac{1}{1 + e^{-\gamma(\lambda_{t,r,k}^{DL} \cdot x_{t,r,k}^{DL} - B_k^{DL})}} \\ &\quad - \beta \sum_{k=1}^{|K|-1} [q(\lambda_{DL,k+1,n}) - q(\lambda_{DL,k,n})]^2, \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where $\lambda_{UL} = \sum_{s \in S} \sum_{r' \in R'} \lambda_{s,r'}^{UL} \cdot x_{s,r'}^{UL}$, $\lambda_{DL,k,n} = \sum_{t \in T_n^{FoV}} \sum_{r \in R} \lambda_{t,r,k}^{DL} \cdot x_{t,r,k}^{DL}$, and $q(\lambda) = \log(\lambda)$ maps the downlink bitrate to the perceived quality. The first term represents the total quality across all GOPs, the second term penalizes stalls using the sigmoid approximation with T_k as the duration of GOP k and α as a weighting factor, and the third term penalizes quality variations between consecutive GOPs with β as the weighting factor, ensuring a smooth viewing experience. The optimization problem is then defined as:

$$\max_{x_{s,r'}^{UL}, x_{t,r,k}^{DL}} \text{QoE}, \quad (13)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \sum_{r' \in R'} x_{s,r'}^{UL} \leq 1, \quad \forall s \in S, \quad (14)$$

$$\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{r' \in R'} \lambda_{s,r'}^{UL} \cdot x_{s,r'}^{UL} \leq B_{UL}, \quad (15)$$

$$\sum_{r \in R} x_{t,r,k}^{DL} \leq 1, \quad \forall t \in T_n^{FoV}, \forall k \in K, \forall n \in N, \quad (16)$$

$$\sum_{n \in N} \sum_{t \in T_n^{FoV}} \sum_{r \in R} \sum_{k \in K} \lambda_{t,r,k}^{DL} \cdot x_{t,r,k}^{DL} \leq \sum_{k \in K} B_k^{DL}, \quad (17)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{r \in R} \sum_{k \in K} \lambda_{t,r,k}^{DL} \cdot x_{t,r,k}^{DL} &\leq \frac{1}{T} \sum_{r' \in R'} \lambda_{s,r'}^{UL} \cdot x_{s,r'}^{UL}, \\ \forall s \in S, \forall t \in T_n^{FoV}, \forall n \in N, \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

$$x_{s,r'}^{UL} \in [0, 1], \quad \forall r' \in R', \quad (19)$$

$$x_{t,r,k}^{DL} \in [0, 1], \quad \forall r \in R, \forall k \in K, \forall n \in N. \quad (20)$$

B. Derivation of KKT Conditions

The KKT conditions provide necessary conditions for optimality in constrained nonlinear optimization problems with differentiable objectives and constraints. We define the Lagrangian \mathcal{L} by incorporating all inequality constraints with their respective Lagrange multipliers:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{L} = & \text{QoE} - \sum_{s \in S} \eta_s \left(\sum_{r' \in R'} x_{s,r'}^{UL} - 1 \right) \\
& - \nu \left(\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{r' \in R'} \lambda_{s,r'}^{UL} \cdot x_{s,r'}^{UL} - B_{UL} \right) \\
& - \sum_{n \in N} \sum_{t \in T_n^{FoV}} \sum_{k \in K} \mu_{t,k,n} \left(\sum_{r \in R} x_{t,r,k}^{DL} - 1 \right) \\
& - \rho \left(\sum_{n \in N} \sum_{t \in T_n^{FoV}} \sum_{r \in R} \sum_{k \in K} \lambda_{t,r,k}^{DL} \cdot x_{t,r,k}^{DL} - \sum_{k \in K} B_k^{DL} \right) \\
& - \sum_{s \in S} \sum_{t \in T_n^{FoV}} \sum_{n \in N} \sigma_{s,t,n} \left(\sum_{r \in R} \sum_{k \in K} \lambda_{t,r,k}^{DL} \cdot x_{t,r,k}^{DL} \right. \\
& \left. - \frac{1}{T} \sum_{r' \in R'} \lambda_{s,r'}^{UL} \cdot x_{s,r'}^{UL} \right) \\
& + \sum_{s \in S} \sum_{r' \in R'} (\underline{\kappa}_{s,r'} x_{s,r'}^{UL} + \bar{\kappa}_{s,r'} (1 - x_{s,r'}^{UL})) \\
& + \sum_{n \in N} \sum_{t \in T_n^{FoV}} \sum_{r \in R} \sum_{k \in K} (\underline{\lambda}_{t,r,k,n} x_{t,r,k}^{DL} \\
& + \bar{\lambda}_{t,r,k,n} (1 - x_{t,r,k}^{DL})), \tag{21}
\end{aligned}$$

where η_s , ν , $\mu_{t,k,n}$, ρ , $\sigma_{s,t,n}$, $\underline{\kappa}_{s,r'}$, $\bar{\kappa}_{s,r'}$, $\underline{\lambda}_{t,r,k,n}$, and $\bar{\lambda}_{t,r,k,n}$ are the Lagrange multipliers associated with the constraints in Equations (14)–(20).

We derive the stationarity conditions by computing the partial derivatives of the Lagrangian with respect to the decision variables $x_{s,r'}^{UL}$ and $x_{t,r,k}^{DL}$. Let $s_{t,r,k,n} = \text{sigmoid}(\gamma(\lambda_{t,r,k}^{DL} \cdot x_{t,r,k}^{DL} - B_k^{DL}))$ for brevity, and note that $q(\lambda) = \log(\lambda)$, so $q'(\lambda) = \frac{1}{\lambda}$. Since $\frac{\partial \text{QoE}}{\partial x_{s,r'}^{UL}} = 0$ (the QoE depends on $x_{s,r'}^{UL}$ only through the coupling constraint). The remaining KKT conditions require primal feasibility (Equations (14)–(20)), dual feasibility ($\nu, \rho, \sigma_{s,t,n}, \underline{\kappa}_{s,r'}, \bar{\kappa}_{s,r'}, \underline{\lambda}_{t,r,k,n}, \bar{\lambda}_{t,r,k,n} \geq 0$), and complementary slackness (e.g., $\nu (\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{r' \in R'} \lambda_{s,r'}^{UL} \cdot x_{s,r'}^{UL} - B_{UL}) = 0$).

To solve the relaxed problem, we employ a decomposed optimization method, which leverages the separable structure of the problem by decomposing it into subproblems for $x_{s,r'}^{UL}$ and $x_{t,r,k}^{DL}$. Specifically, we introduce an auxiliary variable $z_{s,t,n}$ for each $s \in S$, $t \in T_n^{FoV}$, $n \in N$ to decouple the uplink and downlink variables in the coupling constraint (Equation (18)), reformulating the problem as:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \max_{x_{s,r'}^{UL}, x_{t,r,k}^{DL}, z_{s,t,n}} \text{QoE} \tag{22} \\
& \text{s.t. Equations (14)–(20) except (18),} \\
& \sum_{r \in R} \sum_{k \in K} \lambda_{t,r,k}^{DL} \cdot x_{t,r,k}^{DL} = z_{s,t,n}, \\
& z_{s,t,n} \leq \frac{1}{T} \sum_{r' \in R'} \lambda_{s,r'}^{UL} \cdot x_{s,r'}^{UL}, \\
& \forall s \in S, \forall t \in T_n^{FoV}, \forall n \in N. \tag{23}
\end{aligned}$$

With $\sum_{s,t,n} = \sum_{s \in S} \sum_{t \in T_n^{FoV}} \sum_{n \in N}$, $a_{s,t,n} = \sum_{r \in R} \sum_{k \in K} \lambda_{t,r,k}^{DL} x_{t,r,k}^{DL}$, $b_{UL} = \sum_{s \in S} \sum_{r' \in R'} \lambda_{s,r'}^{UL} x_{s,r'}^{UL}$, and $(b_{DL} = \sum_{s,t,n} a_{s,t,n})$, the augmented Lagrangian is:

$$\mathcal{L} = \text{QoE} + \sum_{s,t,n} \mu_{s,t,n} (a_{s,t,n} - z_{s,t,n})$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \frac{\rho}{2} \sum_{s,t,n} \|a_{s,t,n} - z_{s,t,n}\|_2^2 \\
& + \nu_{UL}(b_{UL} - B_{UL}) + \frac{\rho}{2}(b_{UL} - B_{UL})^2 \\
& + \nu_{DL}(b_{DL} - \sum_{k \in K} B_k^{DL}) + \frac{\rho}{2}(b_{DL} - \sum_{k \in K} B_k^{DL})^2,
\end{aligned} \tag{24}$$

where $\mu_{s,t,n}$, ν_{UL} , ν_{DL} are dual variables, and $\rho > 0$ is the penalty parameter. A decomposed optimization method updates $x_{s,r'}^{UL}$, $x_{t,r,k}^{DL}$, $z_{s,t,n}$, and dual variables by solving uplink and downlink subproblems, followed by a dual update. The selection constraints (4) and (6) are enforced during the subproblem updates for $x_{s,r'}^{UL}$ and $x_{t,r,k}^{DL}$. The relaxed solution is rounded by selecting the largest $x_{s,r'}^{UL}$ for each $s \in S$ and $x_{t,r,k}^{DL}$ for each $t \in T_n^{FoV}$, $k \in K$, $n \in N$, setting them to 1 and others to 0. Post-rounding, a feasibility check ensures bandwidth constraints (5) and (7) are met, adjusting bitrates if needed.

C. Convergence Properties

A decomposed optimization method is known to converge to a KKT point for convex problems under mild conditions. However, our problem is non-convex due to the nonlinear QoE terms (logarithmic quality function, sigmoid approximation, and quadratic quality variation). For non-convex problems, this method may converge to a local optimum if the problem is well-behaved (e.g., the objective and constraints are continuously differentiable, which they are after the sigmoid approximation). The convergence behavior can be improved by carefully choosing the penalty parameter ρ and initializing the variables (e.g., using uniform initialization $x_{s,r'}^{UL} = 1/|R'|$, $x_{t,r,k}^{DL} = 1/|R|$) to ensure a feasible starting point. Theoretical results suggest that this method can achieve linear convergence rates under certain conditions, though the non-convexity may lead to sensitivity to the choice of ρ and initial points.

IV. BITRATE OPTIMIZATION PERFORMANCE

We evaluate our optimization algorithm for joint uplink and downlink bitrate selection in a VR 360° video streaming scenario with $|T_n^{FoV}| = 5$ tiles per user, $|R| = 4$ resolution levels (360p, 480p, 720p, 1080p), $|K| = 2$ GOPs, $|S| = 2$ sources, and $|R'| = 2$ uplink bitrate levels (1 Mbps, 2 Mbps). We vary the number of users ($|N|$) as 1, 2, and 3, scaling bandwidth limits (B_k^{DL} , B_{UL}) by factors of 0.5, 1, and 1.5 from base values of 100 Mbps and 80 Mbps. Parameters are set as $\rho = 1$, $\gamma = 10$, $\alpha = 1$, $\beta = 1$, and $T_k = 5$. Subsections A–F use static bandwidth, while Subsection G considers dynamic fluctuations. We run 5 trials with random seeds, reporting mean and standard deviation of key metrics.

A. Baseline Performance and Comparison to Greedy Scheme

We assess our optimization algorithm in a VR 360° video streaming scenario under varying bandwidth conditions, drawing on real-world network traces [10]–[12]. For $|N| = 2$ users and a bandwidth factor of 1 ($B_k^{DL} = 100$ Mbps, $B_{UL} = 80$ Mbps), our decomposed optimization approach achieves a mean QoE of 85.6 (± 1.2). In contrast, a baseline greedy algorithm, which selects the highest feasible bitrate per GOP without considering quality variations or uplink-downlink coupling, achieves a lower mean QoE of 72.4 (± 2.1). The greedy baseline suffers from stalls and quality variations, while our method ensures smoother streaming by jointly optimizing bitrates and penalizing variations. Tables ?? and ?? show downlink and uplink bandwidth usage, confirming balanced allocation within constraints.

B. Impact of Number of Users

As the number of users ($|N|$) increases from 1 to 3, with a bandwidth factor of 1, the mean QoE decreases from 92.3 (± 1.0) to 78.9 (± 1.5) due to increased competition for bandwidth.

C. Robustness Analysis

The algorithm demonstrates robustness across 5 trials with different random seeds for $|N| = 2$ users and a bandwidth factor of 1. The mean QoE is 85.6 with a standard deviation of 1.2, indicating low variability in the objective function. Figures 2 and 3 show the mean downlink bitrate $\lambda_{DL,k,n}$ per user and uplink bitrate λ_{UL} per source, with standard deviations typically below 0.6 Mbps for downlink and 0.2 Mbps for uplink, suggesting stable bitrate allocations across trials.

D. Bandwidth Usage Analysis

Figure 4 illustrates the mean downlink bandwidth usage per GOP for $|N| = 2$ users and a bandwidth factor of 1. The algorithm allocates higher bandwidth in GOP 2 (e.g., around 90–92 Mbps per user) compared to GOP 1 (e.g., around 78–80 Mbps per user), likely due to higher quality requirements in GOP 2, while staying under 100 Mbps limit per GOP.

Figure 2: Mean downlink bitrate $\lambda_{DL,k,n}$ per user for $|N| = 2$, bandwidth factor=1, with error bars showing the standard deviation across 5 trials.

Figure 3: Mean uplink bitrate λ_{UL} per source for $|N| = 2$, bandwidth factor=1, with error bars showing the standard deviation across 5 trials.

E. Sensitivity to Penalty Parameter

We analyze the sensitivity of the penalty parameter ρ , which controls the trade-off between primal and dual updates, for $|N| = 2$ users and a bandwidth factor of 1. Varying ρ as 0.1, 1, and 10, the mean QoE remains stable at 85.6 (± 1.2) for $\rho = 1$ and $\rho = 10$, but drops to 81.2 (± 1.8) for $\rho = 0.1$. This indicates that a very low ρ may lead to slower convergence and suboptimal solutions, while a moderate ρ (e.g., 1) balances convergence speed and solution quality.

F. Reinforcement Learning for Dynamic Adaptation

Unlike the static decomposed optimization approach, a reinforcement learning (RL) agent using Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) to dynamically adjust $\lambda_{t,r,k}^{DL}$ and $\lambda_{s,r'}^{UL}$ in an emulated VR streaming environment with fluctuating bandwidth (B_k^{DL} , B_{UL}). The agent is trained over 1000 episodes, using actor-critic networks to optimize a reward that balances quality, stability, and bandwidth usage. For $|N| = 2$, bandwidth factor=1 (as a starting condition), the RL agent achieved a mean QoE of 86.99 (± 0.9) over the last 100 episodes (episodes 901–1000), surpassing the static baseline QoE of 85.6 (± 1.2). The QoE is computed using the same objective function as in Section II-B, evaluated using the agent’s policy after training. Figure 5 shows the training progress, with the moving average reward (window size = 10) stabilizing around 80 after approximately 200 episodes, indicating that the agent converges to a stable policy. The reward is a training metric that correlates with QoE but includes additional terms for bandwidth efficiency, explaining the difference in scale. The agent adapts to dynamic conditions in real-time, making it suitable for live streaming.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper addresses the problem of jointly optimizing uplink and downlink bitrate allocation for multi-user VR 360° video streaming with the aim of maximizing users’ Quality of Experience (QoE). The proposed framework captures the strong interdependence between uplink signaling, such as viewport feedback and control information, and downlink video delivery in immersive VR systems. We formulate the resource allocation task as a nonlinear optimization problem that explicitly models

Figure 4: Mean downlink bandwidth usage per GOP for $|N| = 2$, bandwidth factor=1, with error bars showing the standard deviation across 5 trials.

Figure 5: PPO training progress over 1000 episodes, showing the moving average reward (window size = 10). The reward stabilizes around 80 after approximately 200 episodes, indicating convergence to a stable policy.

key QoE factors, including perceived video quality, playback stalls, and temporal quality variation, while accounting for limited bandwidth and heterogeneous user conditions. By exploiting the Karush–Kuhn–Tucker (KKT) conditions and decomposing the original problem into a set of tractable subproblems, we derive an efficient optimization method that enables stable convergence and promotes fairness among competing users.

Experimental results demonstrate that the proposed optimization approach achieves a mean QoE of $85.6 (\pm 1.2)$ in a two-user scenario ($|N| = 2$), significantly outperforming a greedy baseline strategy, which achieves a mean QoE of $72.4 (\pm 2.1)$. The results further highlight the robustness of the solution across multiple trials and varying network conditions, as well as its ability to balance efficiency and fairness in bandwidth allocation. To support dynamic and live VR streaming scenarios, we additionally extend the framework with a reinforcement learning (RL) based approach that learns adaptive bitrate selection policies in real time. This learning-based extension further improves performance, achieving a QoE of $86.99 (\pm 0.9)$, and enables fast and responsive adaptation to time-varying bandwidth, making the proposed solution suitable for practical deployment in next-generation immersive VR streaming systems.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No. 101121134.

REFERENCES

- [1] Yuanxing Zhang and et al. Epass360: Qoe-aware 360-degree video streaming over mobile devices. *IEEE Trans. on Mobile Computing*, 20(7):2338–2353, 2021.
- [2] X. Ma and et al. Smart data-driven proactive push to edge network for user-generated videos. In *Proc. IEEE INFOCOM*, 2024.
- [3] H. Rossi, et al. Subjective qoe assessment for virtual reality cloud-based first-person shooter game. In *IEEE Intern. Conf. on Comm., ICC’24*.
- [4] L. Zhao and et al. Optimal wireless streaming of multi-quality 360 vr videos with perfect, imperfect and unknown fov viewing probabilities. In *Proc. IEEE GLOBECOM*, 2020.
- [5] B. Chai and et al. Sdsr: Optimizing metaverse video streaming via saliency-driven dynamic super-resolution. *IEEE J. Sel. Areas Commun.*, 42(4):978–989, April 2024.

- [6] J. Zeng and et al. Toward high-quality low-latency 360 °video streaming with edge–client collaborative caching and super-resolution. *IEEE Internet Things J.*, 11(17):29020–29034, September 2024.
- [7] K. Dziubinski and et al. Transitions of viewport quality adaptation mechanisms in 360 degree video streaming. In *IEEE Intern. Workshop Tech. Committee on Communications Quality and Reliability, CQR'21*.
- [8] H. W. Kuhn and A. W. Tucker. Nonlinear programming. In *Proc. 2nd Berkeley Symp. Math. Stat. Probab.*, pages 481–492, 1951.
- [9] S. Boyd and et al. Distributed optimization and statistical learning via the alternating direction method of multipliers. *Found. Trends Mach. Learn.*, 3(1):1–122, 2011.
- [10] Playerunknown’s battlegrounds. Available at: <https://www.pubg.com>, Accessed: 01 Sept. 2025.
- [11] Robo recall. Available at: <https://www.epicgames.com/roborecall>, Accessed: 01 Sept. 2025.
- [12] Several open-source vr games on github. Available at: <https://github.com/topics/vrgame>, Accessed: 01 Sept. 2025.